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Determination of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of the Role of a Nurse in Achieving Universal Healthcare Coverage among Nurses in Level Three at Kenyatta National Hospital

Abstract: Universal health coverage has been a worldwide agenda since the establishment of sustainable developmental goals. Health for all has been a goal for all nations. In Kenya, health for all is one of the goals of vision 2030 and one of the big four agendas of the current government. Nurses and midwives have been identified as key role players in achieving health for all. Some of their roles include health promotion, research, policymaking, and general quality primary care. This was a cross-sectional hospital-based study that aimed at exploring the knowledge, attitude, and practice of the role of nurses in the achievement of universal health coverage while working in level three (Pediatric wards-3A, 3B, 3C, and 3D) at Kenyatta National Hospital (KNH). The study incorporated 80 consenting respondents following the sample size calculation by Fischer's formula. The Kenyatta National Hospital- University of Nairobi (KNH-UON) Ethical Research Committee granted ethical approval, and the principal investigator ensured that the confidentiality of the participants was upheld and the basic principles of human research applied throughout the whole research process. The study incorporated a research questionnaire as the data collection tool. The collected data was analyzed using SPSS software version 25 following data cleaning and coding. Findings and conclusions: All the nurses reported having heard about Universal Health Coverage (UHC), though most could not define it correctly. The majority have never researched since they started working. Many had moderate knowledge and a positive attitude toward UHC and their role in UHC achievement. They practice their role in quality service delivery by ensuring infection prevention and giving health education when they have time. Recommendations: In collaboration with hospitals and healthcare workers, the MOH and other affiliate agencies should scale up awareness campaigns before implementation. Continual Medical Education (CME) and staff meetings should be used as avenues to scale the level of knowledge among the nurses, being one of the most key stakeholders. The Ministry of Health (MOH) and institutions should provide a conducive working environment for the nurses, such as enough staffing to allow them to practice their roles efficiently and effectively. Institutions should emphasize and provide opportunities for nurses to be involved in research.

Keywords: *Achieving, Attitude, Knowledge, Role, Universal health coverage*

Introduction

Universal health coverage initiated in 1941 is among the top worldwide health agendas. Universal Health Coverage (UHC) means all people and communities receive health services without financial hardship. It includes the whole package of essential, quality health services, from health promotion of healthy lifestyles to prevention of diseases, curative, rehabilitation, and palliative care services (World Health Organization (WHO), 2017). Achieving UHC is among the targets set when adopting the Sustainable Development Goals established by the United Nations General Assembly in 2015. Although all the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have targets that are related to health, the third SDG is the one that mainly focuses on ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all ages. According to WHO (2017), achieving UHC includes protection from financial hardships, access to healthcare services that are quality and essential, and access to safe, effective, quality, and affordable essential medicines and vaccines for all.

Kenya as a country has made progress toward UHC, as evidenced in the various policies, initiatives, and reforms that have been put in place since independence. However, pieces of literature outlined that the healthcare providers have had a low knowledge level on matters related to UHC implementation (Okech et al. 2015). It is not incorrect to say that Kenya as a country is still in its initial stages of implementing UHC and is yet to establish a formal policy declaration on UHC that is entrenched in legislation. This is despite it being reported as having made some progress towards UHC. The implementation of UHC adopts most of its elements from the Kenya Health Policy (2014-2030). The policy objective "to attain universal coverage of critical services that positively contribute to the realization of policy goals" provides a documented commitment to the achievement of UHC for all Kenyans (Obare, Brolan, & Hill, 2014).

Some of the critical strategies that Kenya has already implemented towards achieving Universal Health Care since 2013 include; free maternity services in all public health facilities (3300 facilities), accessible primary health care in all public primary healthcare facilities, equipping major public hospitals across the country with modern diagnostic equipment (94 facilities) where contracts have already been signed up with suppliers, a National Referral Strategy has been developed and piloted, health insurance subsidies through national health insurance targeting disadvantaged groups continues to be implemented and provision of infrastructure and equipment to health facilities across county governments (new wards, ambulances, additional health workers); among others (Strengthening & Sharing, 2018).

The route to Universal Health Coverage (UHC) and the Post-2015 development agenda is through the health workers (Schweitzer, Zoboli, & Vieira, 2016). Nurses play a crucial role in implementing primary health care as a strategy for UHC achievement. Nurses are at the frontline of service delivery; they provide a full range of nursing and midwifery services (which are among the UHC markers) at all health system levels. For nurses to perform their role efficiently, empowerment of the nurses, both qualified and students, through education about UHC is critical. Since nurses have a vital role in UHC implementation, it is not incorrect to outline a considerable knowledge gap in both qualified and training nurses' knowledge in the role of a nurse in UHC achievement.

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A study report from Hong Kong that evaluated the inclusivity of UHC (inclusiveness of elderly) as a UHC implementation strategy discovered a willingness to support the initiative among many institutions, including day centers. However, nurses were shunned away from supporting the initiative due to a significant knowledge gap in the role of a nurse in achieving UHC among the nurses (Tung et al., 2016). In Kenya, it is evident that despite having national policies which are considered politically sound, many have failed to bring the expected because there is a disconnection between the policymakers and implementers, a policy-to-implementation gap. This was alluded to after an analysis of universal health coverage and equity in Healthcare in Kenya was done to review various initiatives that the government has initiated toward the realization of UHC (Okech & Lelegwe, 2016). Nurses are the most significant portion of the healthcare workforce in Kenya, with more than 50% of the total workforce available at all healthcare system levels. In UHC implementation, nurses play a key and active role; hence, the knowledge gap about their role will affect their participation and ownership of the initiative. Therefore, the study proposed assessing the readiness of the Kenyan nurses to embrace and practice their role in UHC achievement by focusing on the assessment of their knowledge and attitude towards the same.

Methods

Study design

The study employed a descriptive cross-sectional study design that utilized a self-administered structured questionnaire to determine the nurses' knowledge level and attitude towards their role in UHC implementation.

Study population

Eligibility criteria for the study included nurses working in the pediatric wards of KNH who consented to participate in the study. The study targeted eligible nurses working in the four pediatric wards 3A, 3B, 3C, and 3D populations. The hospital had approximately 25 nurses in each of the four wards, giving around 100 potential participants. Following the sample size calculation using Fisher's formula coupled with the Cochran formula, a sample of 80 consenting nurses was recruited.

Participants' demographic characteristics

A total of 80 (34 male and 46 female nurses) consented to participate in the study and were hence enrolled. The study had a response rate of 100%, most (45%, $n=36$) of the participants were diploma holders. Most (28.8%, $n=23$) of the participants were senior nursing officers. The majority (60%, $n=48$) of the participants were between the age group of 25-and 35 years. Most of the nurses who participated in the study had practiced nursing for 5-10 years. The majority reported being working in the clinical area mostly. The frequency table below outlines a whole representation of the socio demographic data.

Table 1 Participants demographic variable

Variable		Frequency	Proportion
Gender	Male	34	42.5%
	Female	46	57.5%
	Total	80	100%
Highest education level	Diploma	36	45.0%
	Degree	35	43.8%
	Masters	8	10.0%
	Others	1	1.3%
	Total	80	100%
Cadre of working	NO I	22	27.5%
	NO II	14	17.5%
	NO III	13	16.3%
	SNO	23	28.8%
	ACN	8	10.0%
	Total	80	100.0%
Age group	25-35	48	60.0%
	36-45	22	27.5%
	> 45	10	12.5%
	Total	80	100.0%
Working years	< 5	26	32.5%
	5-10	28	35.0%
	> 10	26	32.5%
	Total	80	100.0%
Area of working	Clinical	62	77.5%
	Management	15	18.8%
	Education	3	3.8%
	Total	80	100.0%

Data collection

The study employed semi-structured questionnaires to gather information from the nurses working in the pediatric wards. The questionnaires were sectioned into four sections, with section A based on socio-demographic data and the remaining three sections A, B, and C based on the established specific objectives; Knowledge of UHC and the role of Nurses in UHC implementation, nurses' attitude towards their role in implementing UHC and the practice of the nurses on their position towards universal health achievement respectively.

Data management

The principal investigator examined the collected questionnaires to ascertain the completeness and correctness of the information gathered. This comprised data cleaning, data coding, data analysis, and presentation of the findings. The principal investigator cleaned irrelevant information before entry of the data into the computer. Data coding involved assigning the different responses numerical values, including 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4, among other values. Coding helps in keying in information into the SPSS software v. 25.0 as it

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does not recognize string variables. The data was then analyzed quantitatively, where the PI generated inferential and descriptive statistics. The PI presented results and findings in frequency column tables, charts including bar graphs and pie charts, and dummy tables.

The level of knowledge was determined using scores, the total scores were summed up to get the knowledge level, and the total scores were 16. 1 through 5 was low knowledge, 6 through 10 was moderate, and 11 through 16 was a high level of knowledge.

The attitude was determined using scores. The total score was 30. The responses were given scores by the PI, which was then summed up to determine the total score that determined the attitude. The positive attitude summed up to 7.

Results

Nurses' knowledge of UHC

All the participants 100% (n=80) reported having ever heard of UHC. Most (33.8%, n=27) of the participants reported having ever heard it via Continual Medical Education (CME). The remaining 21.3% (n=17), 17.5% (n=14), 7.5% (n=6), 7.5% (n=6), and 12.5% (n=10) participants reported having ever heard about UHC through radio/television, social media, someone else and multiple sources of information respectively. Despite the high level of awareness, a smaller percentage, 41.3% (n=33), could correctly define UHC. In comparison, the remaining 58.8% (n=47) were either not in a position to define it correctly or could completely not define it. The participants had a knowledge level mean score, median, and mode of 8.2625, 7.0000, and 7.0, respectively. Most of the respondents, 51.3% (n=41), had a moderate level of knowledge. The remaining 25% (N=20), and 23.7% (n=19), had high and poor knowledge levels, respectively. The findings are presented in the following frequency column table below.

Table 2 level of knowledge

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid LOW KNOWLEDGE	19	23.7	23.8	23.8
Valid MODERATE KNOWLEDGE	41	51.3	51.3	75.0
Valid HIGH KNOWLEDGE	20	25.0	25.0	100.0
Total	80	100.0	100.0	

Nurses' attitude towards their role in UHC implementation

The nurses had a mean attitude, median, and mode scores of 7.3375, 7.0000, and 7.00. The majority of the respondents, 73.8% (n=59), had a positive attitude, whereas the remaining 26.3% (n=21) had a negative attitude towards their role in UHC implementation.

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Figure 1 Attitude and role in UHC implementation

Nurses' practice their role in UHC implementation

The majority of the nurses; 76.3% (n=61), 63.8% (n=51), 85.0% (n=68), 53.8% (n=43), and 46.3% (n=37), reported having been observing the five hand washing moments, using personal protective equipment correctly, segregating their wastes after a procedure, giving health education when they get the time and planning health education as part of their daily plan in the management of patients during service delivery respectively. Lastly, a significant percentage of the nurses, 38.8% (n=31), reported having never participated in the research.

Table 3 Role in UHC implementation

Modes of UHC	Extent of practice	Frequency	Proportion
Use of PPE	Correct use	51	63.8%
	Incorrect use	29	36.3%
	Total	80	100%
Waste segregation after the procedure	Sometimes	12	15.0%
	Always	68	85.0%
	Total	80	100%
Health education	Planned as part of nurses' daily management practice	37	46.3%
	Given out only when the nurse has time	43	53.8%
	Total	80	100.0%
Participation in research	Occasionally	28	35.0%
	Often	21	26.3%
	Never	31	38.8%
	Total	80	100.0%

Discussion

Knowledge: The study found that 25% had high knowledge about UHC implementation and their role in execution; the majority had moderate knowledge, 51.3%. These findings were similar to a study carried out by Biruk and Abet in 2018, who found out that those who demonstrated that 37.6% of the participants had good knowledge of matters related to UHC.

Attitude: The study found that 73.8% expressed a positive attitude towards their role, while 26.3% had a negative attitude. These findings were in harmony with another study carried out by Biruk and Abet in 2018, who found that the majority (64.0%) of the respondents demonstrated a good attitude towards the UHC implementation.

Practice: More than half of the participants (53.8%) reported giving out health education to promote health only when free because of the workload. These findings were similar to those of a study carried out by Keleher and Parker in 2013. In their report, Keleher and Parker (2013) cited that nurses' role in health education was limited, and many did it when they had an opportunity, for example, during wound dressing. In research participation as a measure of the provision of evidence-based practice, the majority, 38.8%, had never done research since they started working. In a similar study done in Yates, it was found by the PI that rarely do nurses involve themselves in research thinking that it is someone else work.

The study found that most participants (63.8%) used PPE appropriately. These findings were contrary to a study done in 2014 by Archana Lakshmi. In her research, Lakshmi (2014) found that only 7% (a smaller percentage of the nurses) who participated in the study used PPE appropriately. The majority (76.3%) of the nurses who participated in the study reported to be observing the five hand hygiene moments while providing care, i.e., before touching a patient, after touching a patient, after touching the patient's surroundings, after exposure to body fluids and before a procedure, these results could be attributed to the thorough campaign on hand hygiene in KNH. These findings contrasted a previously done study by Nfesu Awoke in 2017 that revealed a lower percentage of hand washing practice (18.7%). The study found out that 85% of the nurses in the KNH pediatric wards (level III) always segregated waste, a practice that is deemed effective in providing quality health care. These findings agreed with a previously done study by Girma and Adane in 2019, which revealed that 80% of the study participants had adequate practice scores.

Conclusion

The principal investigator concluded that the achievement of UHC in Kenya is feasible. However, proper education of the key stakeholders is critical as it influences its implementation. A nurse's role significantly impacts UHC achievement, and its outcome is determined by nurse-related factors, including knowledge, attitude, and practice. The nurses' knowledge level of UHC would be considered moderate based on several factors, including the fact that a significant percentage proportion (58.8%) of them could not only correctly define UHC but also their role in the implementation and achievement of UHC. This could be attributed to the limited number of educational and awareness programs on UHC by both the hospital management and the media.

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Many nurses demonstrated a positive attitude towards UHC and their role in its achievement. Therefore, it is correct to say that ownership will be easy given adequate information. In the practice of their role, it is evident that the majority are willing; however, circumstances around them act as barriers. Most nurses have focused on the roles that revolve within the clinical areas, especially in quality service delivery by ensuring proper hand hygiene, personal protective equipment, and proper waste segregation. Most nurses acknowledged that health promotion was part of their daily duty but are unable to practice due to workload hence only practicing it when they have time or when an opportunity arises, for example, during wound dressing. Finally, the majority of the nurses have never participated in research since they started working in evidence-based practice.

In collaboration with hospitals and healthcare workers, the MOH and other affiliate agencies should scale up awareness campaigns before implementation. CME and staff meetings should be used as avenues to scale the level of knowledge among the nurses, being one of the most key stakeholders. The MOH and institutions should provide a conducive working environment for the nurses, such as enough staffing to allow them to practice their roles efficiently and effectively. Institutions should have policies and guidelines that emphasize and provide opportunities for nurses to be involved in research. Future similar studies are done on the role of nurses in achieving UHC in the specific, measurable area.

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